

Psychiatric Morbidity and Quality of Life in Bronchial Asthma Patients undergoing Treatment in Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract

Introduction: Asthma is a chronic inflammatory condition that may cause a disturbance in our routine activities, on sometimes requires a prolonged stay in the hospital. Hence an asthmatic may have episodes of illness throughout their lifetime. This frequent illness has more chance of causing depression and anxiety in them. Like asthma, even a lot of other chronic medical disorders are also related to a lot of psychiatric disorders. Based on this aim of our study is to evaluate the occurrence of anxiety and depression among chronic asthmatics and also in turn how it affects the quality of life. Also, to correlate the control level of asthma with the above factors.

Methodology: This study was done as a cross-sectional descriptive study, at the outpatient Department of pulmonology and Psychiatry in Stanley Medical College, for six months. In our study a hundred patients were included. Spirometry, anxiety level and incidence, depression level and incidence, Quality of life were assessed. Hamilton Rating scale for Anxiety (HAM-A) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) was used.

Results and Conclusion: In our study, thirty-six patients had anxiety and thirty-nine patients had depression. Our study concluded that good asthma control had a lesser incidence of anxiety and depression. Also, patients who had a longer duration of disease had more incidence of psychiatric morbidity than patients with a lesser duration of asthma. In spirometry too there was an inverse correlation with FEV1 /FVC% values. The same relation was seen with quality of life in the above patients. Hence proper control of asthma with earlier treatment will help in reducing psychiatric morbidity. Whereas Good pulmonary function results have a lesser relation with psychiatric morbidity.

Keywords: Anxiety, Depression, Asthma, Control.

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Introduction

Bronchial asthma is a manageable but irrepressible, long-lasting inflammatory lung condition. It is described by unevenness of symptoms and airflow restriction and severity. The inconsistency of symptoms is triggered by elements like a

physical workout, contact with an allergen or irritant, climate changes, and respiratory infection. Symptoms and airflow restriction may reduce spontaneously or in reaction to treatment. Asthma is detected by inconstant expiratory airflow limitation. Uncontrolled

asthma is linked with greater inconsistency in lung function. The spirometry value of Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1) is more trustworthy than that of the Peak Expiratory Flow (PEF). A lesser FEV1 may be seen in multiple lung ailments, but a low FEV1/FVC indicates airflow restriction. There is also a strong relationship between poor control of asthma and greater than before risk of asthma exacerbations [1]. Straight questioning is a vital tool for gauging asthma symptom control on every occasion, including at the time of routine treatment.

Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ). The Score ranges from 0 to 6. A mean score of 0.0 to 0.75 is defined as well-controlled asthma; a score of 0.75 to 1.5 is moderately controlled; and a score >1.5 is poorly controlled asthma.

Asthma is a chronic inflammatory condition that may cause a disturbance in our routine activities, on sometimes requires a prolonged stay in the hospital [2]. Hence, all through an individual's lifespan, he or she may experience exacerbations that can follow with depression and anxiety. Many health illnesses can be related to psychiatric disorders. Many researchers is of opinion that there is a bidirectional effect between depression/anxiety and the severity of the disease.

Numerous comorbid emotional conditions and stress escalate inconsistent respiratory resistance mostly liberated of simultaneous rise in ventilator or autonomic activity and make the patient vulnerable to asthmatic exacerbations [3]. It can have an influence on asthma control symptom awareness and quality of life [4,5].

A German study, conducted by *Goodwin R D et al* among 4181 bronchial asthma patients concluded that there is a significant occurrence of psychiatric illnesses, predominantly depression and anxiety disorders with a compromised quality of life [6] A substantial relationship has been recognized between asthma and anxiety by

multiple studies [7] Even though anxiety is a typical response to severe dyspnea [8] amplified anxiety may cause both exacerbations of asthma and reduced control. Based on this aim of our study is to evaluate the occurrence of anxiety and depression among chronic asthmatics and also in turn how it affects the quality of life. Also, to correlate the control level of asthma with the above factors.

Material and Methods

This study was done as a cross-sectional descriptive study, at the outpatient department of Pulmonary Medicine in Thanjavur Medical College, for a duration of 6 Months. A total of hundred patients were included for analysis. Patients identified with bronchial asthma with age 18 years and beyond, with more than one-year duration of illness, and those who gave informed consent were included in the study. While patients who did not give consent to participate, aged below 18 years, and with a chronic medical were excluded from the study.

Socio-demographic variables were noted, and clinical parameters like duration of illness, family history of asthma, Level of Asthma control, Spirometry measures, Psychiatric Illness Factors, and Quality of life were collected. Hamilton Rating scale for Anxiety (HAM-A) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) was used. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS VERSION 24. Pearson correlation test was used for the evaluation.

Results

A study of hundred asthmatics undertaking treatment in tertiary care hospitals has shown the following outcomes. A greater part of the patients belong age ranging between 41 to 50 years (33%) while only 6% were between 18 to 20 years, 12% were in the age group of 21-30 years, 21% were in 31-40 years, rest were above 60.

In our study, twelve percent of the patients were smokers and only 2 of them were

active smokers, in our study forty-three percent of the patients had a family history of asthma. Coming to control based on ACT questionnaire. 35% of the patients had poorly controlled asthma. 38% were well-controlled and the rest 27% were moderately controlled. Most of the patients had a minimum of one or two visits to OPD every month in the last year. But most of them (91%) did not require admission.

In our study group, 95% of people were taking beta2 agonists. Also, 95% of people were taking Xanthine/Deriphylline, and inhaled steroid was used by fourteen percent of patients. Also, 93% of people were taking antihistamines and leukotriene receptor antagonist was used by 12% of patients.

We next analyzed spirometry values among study participants. The mean FEV1% was 55.55 ± 22.41 , the mean FVC % was 68.6 ± 28.06 , and the mean FEV1/FVC ratio (%) was 73.34 ± 20.86 .

Among our study participants, 21 patients was having a family history of anxiety. Severe anxiety was present in 13 percent of our study population. Whereas moderate anxiety was present in 12 percent of the study population and mild anxiety in 11 percent. Around 36% of our study population had anxiety. The mean anxiety score based on the Hamilton rating scale was 13.5 ± 10.16

Among our study population, 20 of them had a family history of depression Based on Beck Depression Inventory 26 patients had mild depression, 9 patients had moderate depression and 4 patients had severe depression. In total 39 study patients had depression. The mean depression score based on BDI is 9.96 ± 8.3

The mean QOL score among our study population was 4.58 ± 1.25 which was calculated in the range of 1 to 7. Similarly, the mean total AQLQ score is 136.76 ± 37.31 .

In our study population, further we analyzed the relation between various psychiatric presentations with the above parameters related to asthma,

To start with the association between Anxiety and the duration of asthma was done. The statistical test we used was Pearson's which produced substantial results. It showed a positive correlation between Anxiety and the duration of asthma with an r-value of 0.079 which was statistically significant with a p-value less than 0.05. Similarly, correlation tests between Depression and the duration of asthma also produced statistically significant results. With an r-value of 0.301 with a p-value less than 0.05.

Further, we evaluated the association with FEV1/FVC%. There was a noteworthy association between anxiety and FEV1/FVC% in our study population. There was a negative correlation with an r-value of -0.725 and a p-value less than 0.05. Similarly, there is a negative association between depression and the FEV1/FVC % ratio with an r-value of -0.619. This shows that the presence of anxiety or depression may end up having lower FEV1/FVC%. Next, we analyzed Quality of life with FEV1/FVC%. There is a positive association between quality of life and FEV1/FVC % ratio with an r-value of 0.113. The above results prove there is a noteworthy association between anxiety, depression, and QOL with compromise in respiratory function.

Furthermore, we evaluated the relationship between the control of asthma with anxiety and depression. There was a negative association between asthma control and anxiety with an r-value of -0.644 and a p-value less than 0.05. Likewise, there was an inverse correlation between asthma control and depression with an r-value of -0.206 with a p-value < 0.05. Association between asthma control and QOL also had noteworthy results with an r-value of 0.877.

Discussion

The main aim of our study is to evaluate the occurrence of anxiety and depression in chronic asthmatics and its influence on control levels and thereby their consequence on the quality of life. We also made an effort to explore the association of extent of asthma duration and its effect on the disease and modification of the physical and mental health of the patients.

The commonest incidence of age as in a study done by Liam G. Heaney *et al* [9] and other studies ranged between 30- 65 years. Among our patients, most of them were in 41 to 50 years age group and followed by 31 to 40 years.

Hanna *et al* [10] and some other studies stated that women had more prevalence of asthma extending from 62 to 73%. This was similar to our study where 71% of patients were female.

The duration of illness in our study participants varied from 10 to 60 years with a mean range of 13.56 ± 7.98 years. Similar to our study, an Italian study [11] described 12.63 ± 11.25 years while few studies reported variable duration of sickness like 19-23 years by G. Heaney *et al* 11 to 37 years by Antje K *et al* [12].

Also in our study population, longer duration of asthma had a substantial positive association with the presence of anxiety and depression as well as inverse association with FEV1 /FVC%, asthma control, and QOL.

Smoking also had a positive association with the prevalence of anxiety and depression and a negative relationship with the control level of asthma and QOL. Similar to our study, LD Rimington *et al* [13] described depression and anxiety were greater in those who were persistent smokers.

In our study group, 38 percent of patients had good control of asthma based on the ACT Questionnaire, with the remaining 62% having either moderate or poor

control, Vieira AA *et al* [14] study had 40 percent of patients with good control. Whereas in the study by Fabiano DM *et al* [11] 71 percent had good control of asthma.

Most of the patients had a minimum of one or two visits to OPD every month in the last year. But most of them (91%) did not require admission. Comparable to our study in Antje K *et al* [13] study only 2% required admission for exacerbation of asthma. Another study done by Kim LL *et al* [15] reported an increased requirement of admission for patients who were already on treatment.

There was more difference in the mean spirometry values in our study, with FEV1% of 66.23% while the study done by Viera AA *et al* [14] having 72.4%, FVC% was 73.65% while Viera AA *et al* [14] had 88.8% and FEV1 /FVC%-73% while Viera AA *et al* [14] had 80.6%. All these values were bit higher than our study.

If the ratio of FEV1/FVC % is below 75 – 80% it points toward airway obstruction. Our study concludes a severe airway obstruction with a lower FEV1/FVC instigates more anxiety, depression, and poor control of asthma and decreases the quality of life.

As a whole, 36 percent of study population had anxiety and 39 percent was diagnosed with depression. Similar to our study Cobanet *et al* [16] described depression in 47.7 percent and anxiety in 33.3 percent. Similarly, Katon WJ *et al* [17] stated depression in 20 percent and anxiety in 25 percent of their study participants and Samiar AD *et al* [18] stated depression in 24.8 percent and anxiety in 28.7 percent.

Among our study population mean score of QOL (1 - 7) was 4.58 ± 1.25 and total mean score was 146.76 ± 37.3 . Comparable to our study Hikmet *et al* [16] stated mean AQLQ score of 4.3. Kim LL *et al* [15] described the mean AQLQ Score of 5.37 among patients without psychiatric disease and 4.67 among patients with psychiatric disease.

To end with our study exhibited a better level of asthma control had a noteworthy decrease in anxiety and depression, having a substantial development in Quality of life. this was similar to works done by Heaney LG *et al* [9] and Kim LL *et al* [15].

A study by Vieira AA *et al* [14] stated that the incidence of anxiety and depression was considerably greater among poorly controlled than well controlled or moderately controlled asthmatics.

The connection between psychiatric illness, asthma control and asthma-related QOLfe could happen due to multiple factors like behavioral disturbances, disorganized self-care and poor health manners, cognitive or perceptual alterations, ANS and immune systems defect triggered by physiological effects of depression and anxiety.

Due to the presence of long-lasting inflammatory pathology and variable presentation chronic asthmatics have more likelihood of future episodes and reduced pulmonary functions ending up in stress reactions. It has been hypothesized that prolonged emotional stress is a pro-inflammatory state. Few studies also support the theory that stress is related with augmented leukocyte assembly of pro-inflammatory superoxide and cytokines.¹⁹ It is well-known that there is a close association between the struggle in attaining asthma control and psychiatric illness. A multi modal approach is necessary for doctors while treating bronchial asthma. Doctors should be conscious of the fact that anxiety and depressive conditions rise the danger of poor treatment adherence.

Conclusion

Good quality of life and superior asthma control were connected negatively with anxiety and depression. Chronic duration of asthma has an inverse relationship with pulmonary function, asthma control, and quality of life and a positive association with anxiety and depression. Likewise, the

pulmonary function has a positive association with quality of life and asthma control and an inverse association with anxiety and depression. Hence appropriate control of asthma by starting treatment earlier will help in decreasing psychiatric illness.

A large population-based multi-center longitudinal study among children, adolescents, and adults with asthma to measure the prevalence and impact of psychiatric comorbidity are needed.

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